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Abstract

The study aimed to adapt and evaluate the psychometric properties of Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS) for the Bangladeshi population. Items were forward- and committee-translated into Bangla, followed by judge evaluations and pilot testing on 10 respondents. A cross-sectional field study was conducted with a purposive sample of 162 individuals, comprising 81 clinical and 81 non-clinical participants. Psychometric evaluation showed excellent internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.97, and a robust test-retest reliability correlation of 0.87 over a two-week interval. High convergent validity was confirmed via strong correlation with the GHQ-28 ($r = 0.93$), while known-group validity was demonstrated by a significant difference between groups ($F = 1245.84$). Sensitivity and specificity analysis established an optimal diagnostic cut-off score of 29, yielding a perfect area under the ROC curve. Percentile norms defined four severity levels: mild, moderate, severe, and profound.

Cultural Adaptation of the Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale for Use in Bangladesh

Muhammad Kamal Uddin¹, Hasina Khatun²,
Jannatul Ferdous³, and Sabiha Alam Choudhury⁴

Abstract: The present study was intended to adapt and determine the psychometric properties of Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS) with Bangladeshi population. Items were translated into Bangla and evaluated in terms of denotative and connotative meaning according to Bangladeshi culture by judges. The evaluation of each of the judges was assembled by a committee of five experts. Items modification followed by pilot testing on 10 respondents was done to finalize the Bangla version. A cross-sectional study was carried out with 81 clinical and 81 non-clinical respondents following purposive sampling technique. Reliability was established by computing Cronbach Alpha and test-retest reliability. Validity was confirmed through content, convergent and known-group validation. Screening and percentile norms were established by computing the sensitivity and specificity of the scale and by converting raw scores of the clinical samples respectively. Cronbach's Alpha was 0.97 and the correlation between scores on the two administrations was 0.87. Correlation between SCS and GHQ-28 ($r = 0.93$) and difference ($F = 1245.842$) between clinical and non-clinical group provided the evidence for convergent and known-group validity respectively. The sensitivity and specificity analysis indicate the optimal cut-off score of 29. The area under ROC curve of the present scale was found to be 1 indicating that the diagnostic scale is perfect. Four levels of severity namely mild, moderate, severe and profound were set through using percentile norm.

Keywords: somatic complaints scale, adaptation, reliability, validity, norm

Somatic Symptom Disorder (SSD), previously recognized as somatoform disorder, is a mental illness which apparent as bodily symptoms like aching or exhaustion, suggesting the presence of medicinal infirmity (Carson et al., 2003),

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but cannot be elucidated by regular medical clause or by the direct upshot of a substance and are not featured to another mental disorder. This psychological disturbance causes major emotional distress and harms regular functioning of the sufferers. All over the world it is an extensive mental health issue. The pervasiveness of SSD is anticipated to be 5% to 7% of the general inhabitants, with higher female depiction (male-female ratio 1:10) and can transpire in early days, teenage years, or later life (Kurlansik & Maffei, 2016). In Bangladesh, the entire picture of SSD is not different too. A study conducted in National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), Dhaka showed that 6.6% of 849 patients, attending out-patient department, suffered from somatoform disorder (Mohit et al., 2001). In a different study, it was reported that in the outdoor of a psychiatric department of a district hospital, 12.66% of 2923 patients were suffering from having somatic complaints (Hamid et al., 2003). In another study, a total of 1145 respondents aged ≥ 18 years were screened for psychiatric disorders suggesting that SSD was the most common among the respondents (Islam et al., 2003). With an intention to determine the pattern of psychiatric illness among the female patients of psychiatrist's private chamber in Dhaka city, another study was run from May to October, 2014 (Ahmed et al., 2016), and the findings revealed that among the numerous patterns of psychological diseases, depressive disorder was the most common (17.7%), followed by somatoform disorder (14%) and schizophrenia (13.3%). In another report of NIMH (2019), it was revealed that 16.8% Bangladeshi adults suffer from mental health issues and among them 2.1% suffer from somatic symptoms and related disorders.

It has been seen that somatic complaints among the people is rising around the world and Bangladesh is not an exception of it. The need for a common tool to assess the frequency and severity of somatic complaints is utmost essential to fight against this psychopathological problem as per the cultural standards. No standardized scale has yet been developed or adapted in Bangladesh to assess somatic complaints. A standardized Bangla version of a rating scale for somatic complaints assessment like Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS; Morey, 1991) could meet this requirement. SCS is a part of Leslie C. Morey's Personality Assessment Inventory (PAI), which is an internationally well-known, ordered, and simply explicable assessment tool. The Bangla version of Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale with appropriate psychometric properties will be the only one measure of somatic symptom disorder in Bangladesh. In addition, because of the self-rating nature of Morey's SCS, it takes less time, do not necessitate skilled personnel, and its administration and scoring appear consistent as well as standardized. Moreover, the SCS is a moderate length one containing only 24 items. Many studies have

suggested that the performances of these scales are at time even better than the full form or the longer version (El-Rufie & Absood, 1994). Taking all these important aspects into consideration, the present study has been carried out to adapt and determine the psychometric properties of SCS with Bangladeshi population, so that it could be of benefit for the people who would be in the need of it.

Methods

Participants

A total of 162 respondents (81 clinical and 81 non-clinical), age ranging from 18 to 50 years, were taken on the basis of purposive sampling technique from three hospitals of Dhaka city- Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Dhaka Medical College and Hospital (DMCH) and National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), where both inpatient and outpatient psychiatric services along with research facilities were available. As the study was carried out in December, 2010 to April, 2011, the clinical individuals were those who met the diagnostic characteristics of somatoform disorders according to DSM- IVTM and were diagnosed by the psychiatrists, whereas the non-clinical individuals did not meet those criteria and they scored below 39 in GHQ-28 scale. In case of clinical sample, 51 were female (14 conversion, 23 somatizations, 14 hypochondriasis) and 30 were male (3 conversion, 20 somatizations, 7 hypochondriasis). Patients earlier diagnosed with somatization disorder and hypochondriasis usually meet DSM-5 criteria for somatic symptom disorder and illness anxiety disorder (APA, 2013). Both clinical and non-clinical sample were matched in respect of age range and sex. Reticent, puzzled, disoriented, restless, psychotic and having considerable neuro-cognitive impairment were debarred. The details of the demographic information about the participants of the two groups are presented in Table 1.

Measures

Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS), one subscale of the Personality Assessment Inventory (PAI), and Bangla version of the General Health Questionnaire- 28 (GHQ-28) were used in this study. In addition, a personal information form was used to collect the demographic information like age, sex, district, occupation, educational qualification, relationship status, religion, family income per month, birth order, duration of suffering etc. These demographic data were used to match the non-clinical sample with the clinical sample.

Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS). It is a 24-item self-administered scale for individuals above 18 years of age. The items of SCS focus on the

Table 1
Distribution of Demographic Variables of the Clinical and Non-Clinical Sample

Variables		Clinical		Non-clinical		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
		81	100%	81	100%	162	100%
Gender	Male	30	37.03%	30	37.03%	60	37.03%
	Female	51	62.96%	51	62.96%	102	62.96%
Age	18-30	38	46.91%	46	56.79%	84	51.85%
	31-40	31	38.27%	28	34.567%	59	36.41%
	41-50	12	14.81%	7	8.64%	19	11.728%
Occupation	Unemployed	5	6.17%	0	0%	5	3.086%
	Service/job	13	16.04%	12	14.81%	25	15.43%
	Business	10	12.345%	10	12.345%	20	12.345%
	Housewife	41	50.617%	41	50.617%	82	50.617%
Education	Others	12	14.81%	18	22.22%	30	18.518%
	Illiterate	10	12.345%	9	11.11%	19	11.728%
	Class I-V	21	26.25%	14	17.283%	35	21.604%
	Class VI-SSC	30	37.037%	28	34.567%	58	35.802%
	HSC-Graduate	18	22.222%	22	27.160%	40	24.691%
	Post graduate and above (Hafiz, Kamil)	1	1.234%	7	8.641%	8	4.938%
Marital status	Married	68	83.950%	57	70.370%	125	77.160%
	Unmarried	12	14.814%	23	28.395%	35	21.604%
	Others	1	1.234%	1	1.234%	2	1.234%

preoccupation with health issues (Boyle & Lennon, 1994). Three subscales of this scale are SOM-C (somatic conversion, item 1 to 8), SOM-S (somatic somatization, item 9 to 16), and SOM-H (somatic hypochondriasis or health concerns, item 17 to 24). Taking into account the changes for somatoform disorder to somatic symptom disorder in DSM-IV and DSM 5 (APA, 2013), items of SOM-S and SOM-H subscales can be considered for somatic symptom disorder and illness anxiety disorder. It's a 4-point Likert type scale rated through 0 (false or not at all true) to 3 (very true), with a total score ranging from 0 to 72. Item no 11, 12, 21, and 23 are the reverse items. High score in SCS indicates high somatic complaints.

General Health Questionnaire- 28 (GHQ-28). It is a 28-item self-report questionnaire that was used to assess how respondents' health in general had been over the past few weeks, using behavioral items with a 4-point scale ranging from 0 (not at all) to 3 (much more than usual) (Goldberg & Williams, 1988). It assesses the psychological disturbances in terms of both a full-scale score and scores on four subscales, reflecting somatic symptoms, anxiety and insomnia, social dysfunction

and severe depression. But in the present study only the total score was considered that ranges from 0 to 84. Higher GHQ-28 scores indicate higher levels of distress. As it is suggested that researcher can originate a cut-off score based on the mean of their respective sample (Goldberg et al., 1998) in the present study, scores below 39 were considered as not having significant level of psychiatric disturbance and scores >39 were considered as having significant level of psychiatric disturbance. This measure has been reported to have good psychometric properties. In 2001, Banoo translated the GHQ-28 into Bangla and it was found that the test-retest reliability was found to be 0.682 by Spearman's rho.

Procedures

The study was performed in line with the principles of the declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013). The adaptation process of the "Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS)" was accomplished by maintaining the existing ITC (International Test Commission) guidelines (Hambleton, 2001; Vijver & Hambleton, 1996). The adaptation of the SCS consisted of the following five phases.

Phase 1. Translation phase

The items of the SCS were translated in Bangla by using two translation methods- forward and committee translation. In forward translation, the questionnaire is directly translated into target knowledge from its source language and in backward translation the translation is reversed from target language to its source language. Both forward and backward translations deal with the literal meaning only. In committee translation, a group of experts get involve in translating questionnaires from source language to its target language emphasizing more on thematic translation in local languages rather than literal translation of a questionnaire (Peters & Passchier, 2006). Modification of questionnaire is allowed in thematic translation to capture the linguistic and cultural values in the translation process (Kristjansson et al., 2003). Five equivalences (content, semantic, technical, criterion and conceptual) were checked for the present scale.

Forward translation. In this step, items of the SCS were translated into Bangla from English by the researcher who was fluent in both languages, was familiar with the cultures under study and had knowledge of test construction and the construct being measured (Hambleton & Patsula, 1999).

Committee translation. After forward translation, judge evaluation was done to evaluate the initial Bangla version of the scale. The judges were clinical psychologists (9), psychiatrists (7), psychologist (1) and trainee clinical psychologist

(1). At first, each judge was asked to evaluate the initial Bangla version of the scale in terms of denotative and connotative meaning according to Bangladeshi culture. After that, a committee was formed (5 clinical psychologists who were the faculty of the Department of Clinical Psychology, University of Dhaka) to evaluate the previous evaluation of each individual judges. At this time, the committee assembled of each judges' evaluation. After compiling, the items of the scale were being ready for pilot testing.

Phase 2. Pilot testing phase

It was done with 10 respondents (5 diagnosed with somatic symptom disorder and 5 normal individuals) to find out whether they were facing difficulties while responding such as difficulties in understanding instructions, items and response categories of the scale. During pilot testing, they were facing difficulties to understand item 12 and 21. So, these two items were modified. In this step, the researcher herself collected data from respondents. Finally, the items of the scale were being ready for field testing.

Phase 3. Field testing phase

After pilot testing, field testing was done in a large sample (81 clinical and 81 non-clinical) of target population of Bangladesh with reviewed items. In this step, the data was collected by the researcher herself and 3 trained research assistants. The research assistants (Masters Students of psychology department) were provided training on how to administer the questionnaires and collect necessary demographic data from the clients. The researcher and assistants also collected data from 81 non-clinical participants. Rapport was established before collecting data from both types of participants. They were briefed about the general purpose of the study. Both verbal and written consent for participating in the study was taken from them. They were also guaranteed that all information given by them would be kept confidential and would be used only for research purpose.

After collecting all the data from participants, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version-12 was used to analyze the data and prepare the figures.

Phase 4. Determining reliability & validity

The final items of the scale were composed after doing item analysis. Then, the psychometric properties like reliability (internal consistency, test- retest) and validity (content validity, convergent validity, known-group validity) were obtained with the help of SPSS. For internal consistency reliability, Cronbach Alpha was

used. For test-retest reliability, 10 participants diagnosed as having somatic symptom disorder were selected. Content validity was done by judge evaluation. Convergent validity was obtained from the correlation between Somatic Complaints Scale and GHQ-28. The known-group validity was measured with the “*F*” value between two groups (clinical and non-clinical).

Phase 5. Determining norms

Two types of norms, screening and percentile norm, were established for the scale. With the help of SPSS, screening norm was established by computing the sensitivity and specificity of the scale and percentile norm was established by converting raw scores of the clinical samples who got the score 29 and above on somatic complaints scale into percentile norm.

Results

Item Analysis

Two methods- discrimination value and item-total correlation were followed for item analysis of the current scale. The idea behind choosing the discrimination value of items as criterion for the final selection is embedded in the purpose of the scale. The proposed scale will be used to assess clients with SSD. To be effective in diagnosing SSD clients, the scale must be able to discriminate between somatic symptom disorder clients and normal individuals without SSD. The best way to ensure that will be the inclusion of those items in the final scale which have the ability to discriminate between the two groups. For assessing discrimination value of each item, the final scale was administered to two groups of samples comprising a total of 162 subjects (81 clinical and 81 non-clinical). One-way analysis of variance was computed on the two groups (Table 2).

Item-total correlation indicates the internal consistency of the scale. A higher item total correlation of an item indicates the concordance of that item with the construct being measure by the scale. Generally, item total correlation is computed between the item score and the total score of the scale, including the score of the particular item which item total correlation is being measured. This can lead to a bias imposed by that item in the total score as total score is shaped to some extent by the item score. To solve this problem, corrected item total correlation was computed for each item. In corrected item-total correlation, the item score is deleted from the total score before correlating the item with total score (Table 2).

Table 2
Corrected Item-Total Correlation and Discrimination Value F for SCS

Item No.	Corrected item-total correlation	Discrimination value, <i>F</i>
1	.883	468.006**
2	.717	157.312**
3	.814	199.593**
4	.730	140.191**
5	.728	143.657**
6	.785	163.529**
7	.793	199.789**
8	.787	146.961**
9	.910	535.957**
10	.883	429.139**
11	.910	1217.252**
12	.498	57.678**
13	.707	131.810**
14	.750	203.593**
15	.814	257.987**
16	.480	49.843**
17	.812	302.511**
18	.852	361.842**
19	.897	369.659**
20	.683	141.580**
21	.314	20.161**
22	.731	131.310**
23	.843	554.098**
24	.366	22.067**
Total		1245.842**

** $p < .01$

Reliability of the scale

To determine the reliability coefficient of SCS, internal consistency and test-retest reliability were used (Table 3). Internal consistency was assessed by calculating Cronbach's Alpha using data from the respondents from initial administration ($N = 162$). In order to assess the test-retest reliability of the SCS, a total of 10 (3 somatization + 4 conversion + 3 health concern) participants diagnosed as having somatic symptom disorder completed the questionnaire for the second time with an interval of two weeks.

Table 3
Reliability Coefficient of the Bengali Version of Somatic Complaints Scale

	Cronbach's Alpha (<i>N</i> = 162)	Test-retest Correlation (<i>N</i> = 10)
Somatic Complaints Scale	.970	.869**

***p* < .01

Table 3 suggests that the internal consistency of the SCS was satisfactory. Cronbach Alpha was found to be 0.970. Results also indicate that correlation between scores on the two administrations for SCS was .869 which was significant at the 0.01 level.

Validity of the scale

Validation of the SCS was assured by content and construct (convergent and known-group) validity.

Content validity. In the present study, the rigorous systematic steps followed in the adaptation of the present scale can be presented as support for the content validity of the scale. In the adaptation of the SCS, all the items were evaluated by 18 judges and all of them were mental health professionals. A committee was formed with five faculties of the Department of Clinical Psychology of University of Dhaka and this committee finally evaluated the appraisal of previous judges along with their essential remarks. This systematic evaluation indicates the content validity of the scale.

Construct validity. Construct validity of the present scale was assessed using convergent and known-group validity (Domino, 2000). Convergent validity of the scale was demonstrated by the high correlation of the present scale with GHQ-28 (Table 4).

Table 4
Correlation between Somatic Complaints Scale and GHQ-28

GHQ-28 Total	Somatic Complaints Scale
	.925**

***p* < .01

In the process of known-group validation, the present scale's ability to discriminate between two distinct groups (clinical and non-clinical group) of samples was explored. The Somatic Complaints Scale was able to discriminate

between the two groups with a discrimination value of $F = 1245.842$ which was significant at .01 level. Mean and standard deviation of the two groups of the samples are presented in Figure 1. As the present scale possesses both convergent and known-group validity, it is implied that the present scale has construct validity (Mozumder & Begum, 2005; Deeba & Begum, 2004).

Figure 1. Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) of normal and clinical group

Norms of the Scale

Both screening and severity norms were developed for the present scale. The norms were developed based on 81 diagnosed somatic symptom cases and 81 normal cases. The details of the demographic variables of the clinical and non-clinical samples used in developing the norms of the SCS are presented in Table 1.

Screening norm

Sensitivity and specificity

When the results of a particular test or scale considered in two populations, one with a problem, the other without a problem, a perfect separation between the two groups is rarely observed. As presence and absence of problems are two poles of the same continuum, therefore, the distribution of the scale score will overlap. When defining a particular cut-off point or criterion value to discriminate between the two populations, some cases with disease will be correctly classified as positive (TP = True Positive fraction), but some cases with the diseases will be classified negative (FN = False Negative fraction). On the other hand, some cases without diseases will be classified as positive (FP = False Positive fraction), and some cases

without the disease will be correctly classified as negative (TN = True Negative fraction). Thus, four combinations of outcome may occur with every specific cut-off score of a scale (Table 5).

Table 5

Possible Outcomes of a Scale with a Specific Cut-off Score

		Disease	
		Present	Absent
Scale result	Screened Positive	True Positive	False Positive
	Screened Negative	False Negative	True Negative

For the purpose of the screening, the cut-off score of a scale is determined in such a way that the amount of a false negative and false positive is minimal and the amount of true positive and true negative are maximum. This can be done by calculating sensitivity and specificity of a scale. ‘Sensitivity’ of a scale can be defined as the ability to identify the individuals who possess the disease and ‘specificity’ can be defined as the ability of a scale to identify individuals without the disease. In other words, the rates of correct identification of individuals with and without the disease are known as sensitivity and specificity, respectively (Altman & Blend, 1994). For a test to be useful at ruling out a disease it must have high sensitivity, and for it to be useful at confirming a disease it must have high specificity.

In mathematical terms, Sensitivity = $TP / (TP + FN)$ and Specificity = $TN / (TN + FP)$. For the present scale, the sensitivity and specificity were calculated for different cut-off score. A part of the sensitivity and specificity calculation for different cut-off scores including the optimal cut-off score is presented in Table 6.

From the above table we can see that the optimal cut-off score for the present scale is 29, which achieved a sensitivity of 98% and a specificity of 98%. For the present scale, 29 is chosen for cut-off point because the cut-off score has a high sensitivity and a high specificity and the score of sensitivity (98) and the score of specificity (98) is equal.

Diagnostic performance of the scale

The diagnostic performance is the ability of a scale or test to discriminate diseased cases from normal cases. It is usually evaluating using ‘Receiver Operating Characteristic’ (ROC) curve analysis (Zweig & Campbell, 1993). A ROC is a graph that plots the true positive rate (sensitivity) in function of the false positive rate (1-specificity) at different cut-off points.

Table 6
Sensitivity and Specificity of the Present Scale at Different Cut-off Score

Cut-off Score	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
-1	100	0
1	100	1
2	100	2
3	100	7
4	100	17
5	100	23
6	100	38
7	100	54
8	100	64
9	100	69
10	100	77
11	100	82
12	100	84
13	100	85
14	100	88
16	100	90
17	100	92
20	100	96
25	100	97
29	98	98
30	97	100
31	96	100
33	93	100
35	92	100
36	90	100
37	88	100
39	86	100
40	81	100
41	79	100
42	75	100
43	74	100
44	70	100
45	67	100
46	62	100
47	58	100
48	54	100
50	50	100
51	46	100
52	43	100
53	39	100
54	35	100
55	32	100
56	23	100
57	18	100
58	14	100
59	12	100
60	8	100
61	6	100
62	2	100
65	1	100
69	0	100

Figure 2. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for somatic complaints scale

The overall diagnostic performance of a scale can be judged by the position of the receiver operating characteristic line. Poor scales have lines close to the rising diagonal, whereas the lines for perfect scales would rise steeply and pass close to the top left-hand corner, where both the sensitivity and specificity are 1 (e.g. 100%). The area between the ROC curve and the diagonal line is calculated as a measure of diagnostic performance. An area of 1 represents the perfect scale and an area of 0.5 represents a valueless or poor scale. Usually for a scale, an area of 0.90 to 1 is termed as excellent, 0.80 to 0.90 as good, 0.70 to 0.80 as fair, 0.60 to 0.70 as poor and 0.50 to 0.60 as fail. Figure 2 is the receiver operating characteristic curve for the present scale. The area under ROC curve of the present scale was 1 which indicates the perfect diagnostic scale.

Severity norm

Percentile norm was used in developing severity norm for the present scale. For developing the severity norm, the clinical sample who got the score 29 and above on somatic complaints scale was used. Raw scores of the participants of the clinical sample were converted into three percentile points (25th, 50th, and 75th) which divided the scores in four percentile levels (0-25th, 26-50th, 51-75th, 76-100th). These four percentile levels were consecutively used to indicate four level of severity namely mild, moderate, severe and profound. When corresponding raw

score for the percentile range was calculated it was found that for mild, moderate, severe and profound level of severity, the raw scores ranges were 29 to 42, 43 to 50, 51 to 55 and 56 to 72 respectively (Table 7).

Table 7

Percentile Range and Raw Score Range for Corresponding Level of Severity of Somatic Complaints Scale

Severity	Percentile	Corresponding Score on Somatic complaints scale
Mild	0-25	29 to 42
Moderate	26-50	43 to 50
Severe	51-75	51 to 55
Profound	76-100	56 to 72

Discussion

The present study was designed to adapt and establish the psychometric properties of the widely used Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS) for use in Bangladesh. SCS is a 24-item self-report assessment tool that focuses on the preoccupation with health matters and somatic complaints like conversion, somatization etc. The adaptation process was carried out following the ITC guidelines. The outcomes of the present study make sure the usability of SCS in Bangladesh.

Internal consistency and test-retest reliability were carried out to establish the reliability of the Bangla version of Morey's Somatic Complaints Scale. The internal consistency was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha method. Cronbach's Alpha for the SCS was found to be 0.970, which is usually considered as excellent level of internal consistency (De Vellis, 1991). To establish the stability of the current scale in assessing somatic symptom disorder over time, a total of 10 (3 somatization + 4 conversion + 3 health concern) diagnosed somatic symptom disorder patients were selected as participants. SCS was administered to them two times with an interval of two weeks. The correlation between scores on the two administrations was ($r = 0.869, p < .01$) which indicates that the adapted Bangla version of the SCS is highly reliable (Goldberg & Williams, 1988) to use as the value is also similar with original English, $r = 0.73$.

Validation of the instrument was assured by content and construct validity. Satisfactory level of validity was found for the adapted Bangla version of Somatic Complaints Scale. Content validity of the adapted version of the scale was ensured during the different steps of adaptation. Inclusion of large number of (18) mental

health experts as judges also provides indication of content validity of the present scale (Johnston et al., 1992). Beside this, a committee was formed with five faculties of the Department of Clinical Psychology of University of Dhaka and this committee finally evaluated the appraisal of previous judges. This systematic evaluation also indicates the content validity of the scale. Evidence for the construct validity of the present scale was accumulated from convergent and known-group validation (Domino, 2000). High and significant correlation of Somatic Complaints Scale ($r = 0.925, p < 0.01$) with GHQ-28 indicated the evidence for convergent validity and significant difference ($F = 1245.842, p < .01$) between clinical and non-clinical group provided the evidence for known-group validity.

The sensitivity and specificity analysis of the scale indicates the optimal cut-off score for the present scale is 29. The sensitivity of 98% indicates that the scale will be able to correctly identify 98% of the cases and only 2% of the cases will be missed. And a specificity of 98% meaning that the scale will be able to correctly identify 98% of the non-cases but at the same time 2% of the non-cases will be wrongly indicated as case. The diagnostic performance of the scale was assessed by ROC curve (Figure 2). The area under ROC curve of the present scale was found to be 1 indicating that the diagnostic scale is perfect. This ROC curve indicates excellent diagnostic performance of the present scale.

Four levels of severity namely mild, moderate, severe and profound were set for Somatic Complaints Scale through using percentile norm. The corresponding scores of the Somatic Complaints Scale for these different severity levels were found to be 29 to 42, 43 to 50, 51 to 55 and 56 to 72 respectively (Table 7).

The findings of the present study can be considered to imply that the adapted Bangla version of Somatic Complaints Scale (SCS) is suitable for assessing one's preoccupation with health matters in Bangladeshi context. But, like many other studies, this study also suffers from numeral limits. Development of norm requires a normative sample which should be representative of the population and one way to get the representative sample is to use random sampling technique. In the present study random sampling was not possible as the sample required to possess a specific disorder (somatic symptom disorder). For this reason, purposive sampling technique was used as a way to achieve representativeness of the sample.

Although, data from both clinical and non-clinical samples were collected with the help of three trained research assistants, but administration of the scale does not require any expertise, only a brief introduction on the scale is enough. The scale is a self-report and self-administered measure, but it can also be used as clinician administered especially where the client is unable to read or write. Self-

administration of the scale requires about 8 to 10 minutes. If the scale is used in screening purpose, it should be accompanied by clinical interview for the diagnosis and interpretation to be made.

To reach perfection, every scale needs to undergo review and enrichment by follow-up studies. In future enhancement of the present scale backward translation may be used. The study took place in three hospitals of Dhaka city- BSMMU, DMCH and NIMH, where both inpatient and outpatient psychiatric services along with research facilities were available. Usually, patients from all over Bangladesh come here for treatments, even though it would be better if a representative sample could be collected from all over the country to develop norms. In addition, a large sample would increase the confidence of reporting the norms (screening & severity norms) in interpreting somatic symptom disorder.

Conclusion

Very few tools have been developed/ adapted in our country for clinical use. The clinical psychologists of our country have developed only three scales for assessing depression, anxiety and obsessive-compulsive disorder for use in Bangladeshi culture. Adapted Bangla version of Morey's somatic complaints scale will be another assessment tool for use in Bangladesh to assess somatic complaints of an individual. The need of such a scale was felt for long by the mental health professionals of Bangladesh. The present scale will meet that need and the findings can serve as a base or open the door of further research.

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